

Projected Net Carbon Emission Limit (PNCEL): A Dynamic Model for Carbon Management in Agroforestry Systems

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Abstract

Purpose | Agricultural and agroforestry systems have been shown to have a significant impact on greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, whilst simultaneously presenting considerable opportunities for carbon sequestration. Nevertheless, the quantification and projection of their net carbon balance continue to represent a considerable challenge. This study introduces the Projected Net Carbon Emission Limit (PNCEL), a new metric applied in a dynamic model designed to measure and project the carbon footprint in agroforestry systems by integrating direct emissions, soil carbon sequestration, and net carbon balance. The model aims to support sustainable business management, inform public policy formulation, and facilitate academic research on soil management's impact on emission reductions. **Methodology/Approach** | The PNCEL model integrates advanced temporal monitoring with carbon management metrics for agricultural and agroforestry production chains, enabling the assessment of the net effectiveness of mitigation strategies and providing evidence-based operational recommendations. The model incorporates data from GHG inventories, aligning with international standards such as the GHG Protocol and ISO 14064. The model employs dynamic equations to calculate Absolute GHG Emissions, Net Carbon Balance (NCB), and the Projected Net Carbon Emission Limit (PNCEL), allowing the net effectiveness of mitigation strategies to be assessed and providing operational recommendations for long-term scenarios. Although initially applied in viticulture, the model's flexibility allows for its adaptation to other sectors, including olive cultivation, fruit production, and integrated agroforestry systems. Beyond its application in sustainable business management, the model can be utilised by regulatory bodies for public policy formulation and by academic institutions to study the impact of soil management on emission reductions. **Expected Results** | Future projections indicate that the PNCEL can be enhanced through integration with machine learning and artificial intelligence, expanding its applicability to a broader range of agricultural activities and evolving into a standardised carbon neutrality index. The model's dynamic and flexible approach supports the creation of tailored decarbonisation strategies, contributing to the sustainable transition of agroforestry systems and the achievement of global climate goals, such as those outlined in the Paris Agreement. **Practical Implications** | The model holds significant potential for guiding agro-environmental policies, enabling the design of performance-based incentive programs, supporting carbon certification schemes, and informing extension services for farmers seeking climate-positive management. However, its full institutional adoption will require further empirical validation and robust verification mechanisms for farmer-reported data.

Keywords | Carbon Management, Climate Neutrality, Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) Sequestration, Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA), Viticulture, Regional development, Environmental policies.

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1. Introduction

The climate emergency and the increasing demand for carbon neutrality in agri-food systems have driven the development of tools for quantifying greenhouse gas emissions and carbon sequestration at multiple scales. Agriculture—particularly viticulture—faces regulatory, market, and environmental pressures to integrate climate performance metrics into production processes and certification schemes (Pinto da Silva & Esteves da Silva, 2022). However, the methodological field remains fragmented, lacking parameterized, auditable models that are adaptable to the diversity of local production contexts (Flores, 2018; Merli et al., 2018).

Several international frameworks have been developed to promote sustainability in the wine sector, such as Sustainability In The Italian Wine Sector – VIVA (Italy), California Sustainable Winegrowing Alliance – CSWA (California), and the Eco-Management and Audit Scheme – EMAS (European Union). While these models represent significant progress, they also reveal critical gaps in the standardization of climate-related indicators and their practical integration with public policies (CSWA et al., 2020; Marta-Costa et al., 2022). The literature further highlights the challenges of applying conventional Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) approaches to small-scale farms, due to technical complexity and high implementation costs (Cichelli et al., 2016; Montalvo-Falcón et al., 2023).

In the Portuguese context, studies have demonstrated the need for operational tools capable of assessing and guiding climate sustainability in the field, based on scientific evidence and territorial adaptability (INE, 2019; Trigo et al., 2023). Nevertheless, national sustainability indicators lack granularity and direct applicability to the agricultural sector, particularly with regard to soil and cultural practices.

The absence of an auditable methodological model that links agricultural practices to continuous carbon metrics constitutes a significant technical gap (Nikolaou & Tsalis, 2013; Baiano, 2021). This gap is further reinforced by the lack of a binding European legal framework for soils, as highlighted in the LILAS4SOILS report (Dobarco et al., 2024), and by the regulatory fragmentation that hinders coordination between agricultural management, GHG inventories, and certification mechanisms (The Greenhouse Gas Protocol, 2004; European Parliament and Council, 2021, 2024).

In this context, the PNCEL model emerges as an innovative methodological proposal. Inspired by the principles of relevance, consistency, completeness, and auditability as defined by ISO 14064-1:2018 (ISO, 2018) and ISO 14064-3:2019 (ISO, 2019), as well as by the GHG Protocol (The Greenhouse Gas Protocol, 2004), the model functions through continuous interpolation across management bands, using a weighted checklist of practices based on their estimated contribution to carbon emissions or sequestration (Yaman, 2024; Tombak et al., 2025).

In addition to its technical alignment with existing standards, the model responds to the sociotechnical critique that environmental measurement tools shape the political and economic infrastructures in which they are embedded (Moscovici & Reed, 2018). By translating production practices into operational metrics, the PNCEL model provides climate diagnostics, planning, and eligibility for programs such as the CAP Strategic Plan 2023–2027 (Gabinete de Planeamento, n.d.), the RNC2050 Strategy (RNC2050, n.d.) and the new European carbon certification system (European Parliament and Council, 2024).

This article presents the methodological framework, normative foundations, and practical applications of the PNCEL model. Its comparative advantages over existing systems, limitations, and potential for integration into climate public policies are discussed, based on empirical simulations conducted with contrasting profiles of wine producers in the Portuguese context. This work thus aims to strengthen climate governance in the agricultural sector by proposing a replicable, transparent model that is sensitive to the specificities of contemporary viticulture.

2. Methodology

Methodological Objective

This study proposes the formulation and application of a semi-quantitative model for assessing climate performance in viticulture, referred to as PNCEL. The model was designed to integrate agricultural practices into an interpolable metric of net carbon emissions, based on the methodological principles defined by the GHG Protocol (The Greenhouse Gas Protocol, 2004), ISO standards 14064-1:2018 (ISO, 2018) and ISO 14064-3:2019 (ISO, 2019).

Sources and Criteria for Parameterization

The definition of minimum and maximum parameters for emissions and sequestration was based on a critical review of scientific studies that quantify carbon fluxes in viticulture, prioritizing literature set in agroclimatic contexts similar to that of Portugal (Payen et al., 2021; Schultz, 2022; Xue et al., 2024). The detailed inclusion criteria for the selection of these studies are presented in Section 4.

Structure of the PNCEL Model

The model was developed in five main stages: (i) construction of a technical checklist comprising 27 agricultural practices organized into functional categories; (ii) assignment of weights to each practice based on three criteria: magnitude of impact, frequency of adoption, and scope of climate effect (The Greenhouse Gas Protocol, 2004; Wahyudi et al., 2018); (iii) grouping of practices into three management regimes (conventional, conservation-oriented, regenerative); (iv) definition of minimum and maximum parametric values for each regime, based on the ranges reported in the literature; (v) development of a linear interpolation for estimating net emissions.

Interpolation and Algorithmic Structure

Interpolation is performed between the minimum and maximum parametric values defined for each management band. The model is calculated as the difference between estimated emissions (E_i) and estimated sequestration (S_i), with interpolation proportional to the weighted sum of the adopted practices. A tolerance range of $\pm 5\%$ is applied to account for operational and agronomic uncertainties, as suggested by Dekay (2017). This approach enables continuous, auditable, and replicable estimates.

Model Application: Simulation of Production Profiles

Three simulated profiles of wine producers (small, medium, and large) were defined based on representative patterns of the Portuguese sector, according to data from the National Statistics Institute (INE, 2019) and the Institute of Douro and Port Wines (IVDP, 2025). The simulations were constructed based on practices assigned to each profile, varying according to a management transition logic (from conventional to regenerative). The simulations were constructed based on practices assigned to each profile, varying according to a management transition logic (from conventional to regenerative). This is an ex ante methodological experiment using projected, non-observational data, following the approach adopted by Oblitas-Romero et al. (2023).

Normative Alignment and Auditability Potential

The PNCEL model was designed to be auditable and compatible with the quantification and verification principles established by ISO 14064-1 (ISO, 2018) and ISO 14064-3 (ISO, 2019), allowing for external verification of data and weighting factors based on document traceability. Moreover, its structure facilitates integration with Scope 1, 2, and 3 reporting systems under the GHG Protocol (The Greenhouse Gas Protocol, 2004), thereby broadening its applicability.

3. Comparison Between the PNCEL Model and Existing Composite Indices

In the current context of rapid development in climate performance indicators, this section compares the PNCEL model with existing composite indices. The aim is to position PNCEL and highlight its originality, particularly in light of the gaps identified in models that, although robust, lack adaptability and methodological consistency across different operational contexts (Aristizábal-Alzate & González-Manosalva, 2021; Oblitas-Romero et al., 2023; Tombak et al., 2025).

To assess the positioning and originality of the PNCEL model within the viticulture context, this section presents a comparative analysis with other relevant composite indices found in the scientific literature.

Among the indices considered, the Carbon Sequestration Potential Index (CSPI), proposed by Pascual et al. (2021), presents structural similarities by integrating various environmental variables—such as gross primary productivity, aboveground carbon density, and forest cover—through weighted interpolation. However, its application is geared toward the territorial scale, relying on remote sensing and spatial modeling, which distances it from the operational approach of the PNCEL model, which is centered on the farm unit and based on annual diagnostics. Nevertheless, the CSPI represents an important methodological reference, particularly regarding the normalization structure of indicators and the use of physical proxies derived from environmental data.

The Carbon Balance Index (CBI), developed by Dekay (2017), is applied to the construction sector and proposes a metric for evaluating buildings based on their carbon performance, analogous to the Energy Use Intensity (EUI). Although operating in a distinct sector, the CBI shares with the PNCEL model the logic of parameterized interpolation across performance zones, based on normative targets. Both models employ tolerance ranges to classify units according to their alignment with a neutrality trajectory, albeit using different input variables and application objectives.

The Carbon Sequestration Index (CSI), described by Wahyudi et al. (2018), proposes a ratio between total carbon sequestered (in biomass and sediments) and total emissions within a given area, primarily applied to coastal ecosystems. Its most direct similarity to the PNCEL model lies in the core logic of balancing emissions and sequestration. However, the CSI does not account for specific management practices nor does it differentiate between production regimes, which limits its operational diagnostic capacity. By incorporating specific agricultural practices with defined weights, the PNCEL model offers greater granularity and adaptability to agricultural contexts.

Finally, the CCS Readiness Index, developed by the Global CCS Institute (Consoli et al., 2017), although not a direct indicator of environmental performance, is a composite index designed to assess institutional readiness for implementing carbon capture and storage technologies. Its multidimensional qualitative structure provides a useful counterpoint for reflecting on the strategic applicability of the PNCEL model as a policy support tool. By integrating both technical and institutional aspects, the CCS Readiness Index underscores the importance of models such as PNCEL, which are not only operational but also decision-oriented.

Table 1 summarizes the key points of comparison between the analyzed indices and the PNCEL model, highlighting similarities and differences in terms of calculation logic, type of data used, unit of application, and institutional applicability.

Table 1. Comparison between the PNCEL model and composite carbon assessment indices

Index	Application Sector	Input Variables	Calculation Logic	Similarity to PNCEL
CSPI	Land use/forestry	GPP, ACD, FC (remote sensing)	Weighted interpolation with NIR _v	Moderate - spatial index structure
CBI	Construction	Operational and embodied emissions	Index normalized by performance zones	Conceptual - normative interpolation
CSI	Coastal ecosystems	Total sequestration vs. aggregate emission	Direct ratio (Tseq+Mseq)/Aems	High - net balance logic
CCS	Public policies	Institutional qualitative indicators	Multi-criteria composite index	Strategic - decision support function

The analysis shows that, although the PNCEL model shares methodological elements with existing composite indices, it stands out for its emphasis on the production unit, its operationalization through a checklist, and its parameterized interpolation based on agricultural practices. These features make it an original and pragmatic proposal for annual climate diagnostics in viticulture, with methodological consistency and potential for policy application.

4. Emission and Sequestration Parameters

Modeling the dynamics of greenhouse gases (GHGs) in viticulture requires the definition of robust quantitative parameters for carbon emissions and sequestration per unit area. This section presents the values used in the PNCEL model to represent these fluxes, based on a critical analysis of scientific literature focused on the quantification of gross emissions and carbon sequestration potential in viticultural systems. The aim is to establish a comparable empirical basis with direct applicability to the Portuguese agricultural and climatic context, particularly with regard to vineyards in temperate Atlantic and Mediterranean climates (Brunori et al., 2016; Martins et al., 2019; Novara et al., 2020).

In the context of carbon balance modeling for agroecosystems, it is essential to differentiate between the various carbon pools and the dynamic processes that govern both sequestration and storage. These pools include atmospheric CO₂, above-ground biomass (such as leaves, stems, and fruit), below-ground biomass (notably roots), dead organic matter (including litter and pruning residues), and particularly the soil organic carbon (SOC) fraction. This conceptual framework is widely recognized in viticultural systems (Williams et al., 2020; Schultz, 2022; Xue et al., 2024; Almeida Santos, 2025).

The PNCEL model focuses specifically on two core components: (1) direct greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from agricultural practices such as fertilizer application, fossil fuel combustion, and pesticide use (Adoir et al., 2020; Cech et al., 2022; Galdino & Signor, 2024), and (2) the net accumulation of atmospheric carbon into the SOC pool as influenced by soil management strategies. The latter includes practices like permanent cover cropping, compost application, and the cessation of tillage — all of which have demonstrated significant potential to enhance SOC stocks (Brunori et al., 2016; Novara et al., 2020; Payen et al., 2021).

Although carbon retained in plant biomass contributes meaningfully to short-term storage and nutrient cycling, it is the increase in SOC that provides long-term, stable sequestration — a

dynamic recognized as central to climate mitigation in perennial cropping systems (Song et al., 2023; Villat & Nicholas, 2023). The PNCEL model adopts this perspective, prioritizing SOC gains as the key indicator of carbon sink functionality within viticultural landscapes.

Empirical studies, modeling efforts, and systematic reviews that quantify GHG emissions or carbon sequestration in viticultural systems were considered. Inclusion was limited to articles reporting results in units compatible with the model (Mg CO₂-eq/ha/year), with clear methodology aligned with Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), RothC, Net Ecosystem Exchange (NEE), or regional agricultural inventories. Priority was given to studies focused on European territories with climates comparable to that of Portugal (Payen et al., 2021; Schultz, 2022; Xue et al., 2024).

The reviewed literature reveals significant variation in gross emission and carbon sequestration values. In the case of emissions, values range from 0.3 to 25 Mg CO₂-eq/ha/year, depending on factors such as management type, mechanization, irrigation, use of synthetic fertilizers, and transportation distance (Adoir et al., 2020; Litskas et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2021). Regarding sequestration, values range from 0.5 to 12 Mg CO₂-eq/ha/year, with emphasis on practices such as permanent cover cropping, composting, no-tillage systems, and the integration of functional biodiversity (Payen et al., 2021; Villat & Nicholas, 2023; Xue et al., 2024).

5. Methodological Structure of the Model: Technical Classification, Interpolation, and Projection of Net Emissions

5.1. Classification of Agricultural Practices by Impact

The weights assigned to agricultural practices in the PNCEL model are not based on an absolute scale of impact, but rather on a relative hierarchy that considers three main criteria: (i) the expected magnitude of the practice's climate impact (avoided emissions or estimated sequestration); (ii) the frequency of occurrence in regional production systems; and (iii) the spatial and functional scope of the practice (for example, practices that directly affect the soil, such as tillage or cover cropping, are assigned higher weights due to their central role in the carbon cycle).

These criteria were applied in an integrated manner to assign simplified weights that preserve the model's functionality while ensuring methodological soundness. Tables 2 and 3 consolidate the selected practices and their respective weights, based on empirical references and expert scientific review.

The validity of this structure is supported by studies such as Montalvo-Falcón et al. (2023), which demonstrate that the use of practice-based composite indicators is not only operationalizable but preferable in small- and medium-scale agricultural contexts, where approaches based on LCA or direct inventories are often constrained by limited data and resources.

Table 2. Practices associated with carbon emissions and their respective weights.

Category	Practice	Weight	Reference
Fertilization	Use of synthetic nitrogen applied as full coverage	3	Galdino & Signor (2024)
Pesticides	Intensive synthetic applications (>4/year)	2	Cech et al. (2022)
Irrigation	Irrigation using non-renewable electric matrix	2	Zhang et al. (2021)
Mechanization	Diesel tractor use >100 h/ha/year	3	Adoir et al. (2020)
Soil preparation	Deep tillage	2	Novara et al. (2020)
Transport	Distance >100 km from vineyard to winery	1	Martins et al. (2019); Pinto da Silva & Esteves da Silva (2022)

Table 3. Practices associated with carbon sequestration and their respective weights.

Category	Practice	Weight	Reference
Cover cropping	Permanent living cover between rows	3	Schultz (2022); Xue et al. (2024)
Composting	Application >5 t/ha/year	2	Payen et al. (2021)
Soil management	No-tillage	2	Villat & Nicholas (2023)
Biodiversity	Presence of native vegetation/riparian buffers	1	Williams et al. (2020)
Animal integration	Rotational grazing between rows	2	Villat & Nicholas (2023)
Vineyard age	Vines younger than 15 years	1	Song et al. (2023)

The practices are organized into two main groups:

- Practices with emission impact (Table 2);
- Practices with carbon sequestration potential (Table 3).

The selection was based on specialized scientific literature, with an emphasis on studies applied to viticultural systems in Mediterranean and Atlantic climates. Each practice was assigned a weight proportional to its relative contribution to the carbon balance, grounded in empirical estimates or validated technical inference.

The weighting scale ranges from 1 (low impact), 2 (moderate), to 3 (high), and is mirrored for both groups of practices. The overall structure is summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. Weighting System for Agricultural Practices Based on Carbon Emission and Sequestration Impact.

Weight	Emitting practices (negative impact)	Sequestering practices (positive impact)
3	High emissions (e.g., nitrogen fertilization)	High sequestration (e.g., permanent vegetation cover)
2	Moderate emissions (e.g., intensive mechanization)	Moderate sequestration (e.g., organic composting)
1	Low emissions (e.g., transportation >100 km)	Light sequestration (e.g., riparian vegetation)

5.1.1. Scoring and Normalization

The model assumes the following theoretical limits:

- A maximum of 6 emission-related practices \times maximum weight (3) = 18 negative points;
- A maximum of 6 sequestration-related practices \times maximum weight (3) = 18 positive points;
- Theoretical maximum total: 36 weighted points.

Each practice selected by the producer in the technical checklist is converted into a weighted score, and the result is expressed separately for emission practices

(P_E) and sequestration practices (P_S). These values are directly used for emission and sequestration interpolation, as described in section 5.3.

For the purpose of management type classification (section 5.2) and visualization within the evaluation system, the total score ($P_S + P_E$) is converted into a percentage scale ranging from 0 to 100, through the following linear normalization:

$$\text{Normalized score} = \left(\frac{P_S + P_E}{36} \right) \times 100$$

Thus:

- 18 total points (e.g., $P_S = 18, P_E = 0$) correspond to 50 (beginning of *Conservationist* category);
- 27 points (e.g., $P_S = 27, P_E = 0$) correspond to 75 (beginning of *Regenerative* category)

This conversion enables the use of the ranges defined in Table 5 for the interpolation of E_i and S_i , without compromising the technical integrity of the evaluation system.

5.2. Management Type Categorization and Scoring

The classification of management type in the PNCEL model is based on the total technical score assigned to the set of agricultural practices identified in the field, as described in section 5.1. The score obtained by each producer is normalized to a 0–100 scale and, based on this value, the producer is classified into one of three interpretive categories: *conventional*, *conservationist*, or *regenerative*.

Each of these categories is associated with a range of technical values for gross carbon emissions (Mg CO₂-eq/ha/year) and carbon sequestration potential (Mg CO₂-eq/ha/year), defined through a consolidation of empirical evidence, modeling studies (such as RothC), and methodologies based

on life cycle assessment (LCA). The sources used prioritize contexts compatible with viticultural systems in Mediterranean and Atlantic climates, ensuring the relevance and applicability of the adopted ranges.

The construction of these ranges is not based on a one-to-one association between study and value, but rather on a technical-interpretive grouping that ensures methodological coherence and comparability across different sources. This semi-quantitative approach allows for continuous interpolation of values within each range, maintaining the model's flexibility without compromising scientific consistency.

Table 5 presents the emission and sequestration ranges associated with each management category, as well as the corresponding normalized score intervals. These ranges are used in the linear interpolation equation (section 5.3) to estimate, based on the producer's individual score, the interpolated values of gross emissions E_i and potential sequestration S_i , which feed into the model's annual net emission calculation.

Table 5. Carbon Emission and Sequestration Ranges by Management Classification Score.

Type of Management	Score Range (normalized)	Emission Range (Mg CO ₂ -eq/ha/ano)	Sequestration Range (Mg CO ₂ -eq/ha/ano)	References
Conventional	0 to 49	14 to 25	0,5 to 2,3	Adoir et al. (2020); Zhang et al. (2021); Galdino & Signor (2024); Schultz (2022); Novara et al. (2020)
Conservationist	50 to 74	5 to 10	4,0 to 7,5	Litskas et al. (2020); Pinto da Silva & Esteves da Silva (2022); Cech et al. (2022); Brunori et al. (2016); Payen et al. (2021)
Regenerative	75 to 100	1,5 to 3,0	8,0 to 12,0	Williams et al. (2020); Schultz (2022); Villat & Nicholas (2023); Xue et al. (2024)

The classification of management type is operationalized through a checklist of agricultural practices, in which each practice is assigned a weight proportional to its estimated contribution to emissions or carbon sequestration. The producer's total score determines their placement in one of the three management categories. This total score is then used to interpolate values within the specific range corresponding to the assigned category, enabling the estimation of the model's annual net emission value.

5.3. Interpolation and Calculation of Annual Net Emissions

The annual net carbon emission estimated by the PNCEL model is obtained by subtracting the interpolated carbon sequestration from the interpolated gross emissions, according to the equation:

$$EL_0 = E_i - S_i$$

Where:

- EL_0 : net annual carbon emission in the reference year (baseline);

- E_i : interpolated value of the estimated gross emissions;
- S_i : interpolated value of the estimated sequestration potential.

Both E_i and S_i are calculated through linear interpolation based on the technical score obtained by the producer in the assessment of agricultural practices, according to the identified management type (conventional, conservationist, or regenerative). The lower and upper bounds of the emission and sequestration ranges used in this calculation are defined based on the consolidated technical intervals per management type, as presented in Table 5.

The general linear interpolation formula used in the model is:

$$V_i = V_{min} + \left(\frac{P - P_{min}}{P_{max} - P_{min}} \right) \times (V_{max} - V_{min})$$

Where:

- V_i : interpolated value (can represent either E_i or S_i);
- V_{min}, V_{max} : lower and upper bounds of the value range (emissions or sequestration) defined for the management type;
- P : score obtained by the producer (for emission or sequestration impact);
- P_{min}, P_{max} : lower and upper bounds of the possible score range for the evaluated practices.

Formula Applications:

- To estimate E_i , use: $E_{min}, E_{max}, P_E, P_{E\ min}, P_{E\ max}$;
- To estimate S_i , use: $S_{min}, S_{max}, P_S, P_{S\ min}, P_{S\ max}$.

This structure allows for continuous interpolation within each range, adapting to gradual changes in implemented agricultural practices. As such, the model is sensitive to technical progress even within a single management regime, enabling more precise assessments of productive dynamics. Table 6. Definition of the parameters used for interpolation in the PNCEL model.

Table 6. Definition of parameters for interpolation in the PNCEL model.

Symbol	Definition
EL_0	Annual net emission in the baseline year
E_i	Gross emission interpolated based on the technical score of emission practices
S_i	Potential sequestration interpolated based on the technical score of sequestration practices
P_E	Total score from agricultural practices with emission impact
$P_{E\ min}, P_{E\ max}$	Lower and upper bounds of technical scores for emission practices, by management type
E_{min}, E_{max}	Lower and upper bounds of the emission range for the given management type
P_S	Total score from agricultural practices with sequestration impact
$P_{S\ min}, P_{S\ max}$	Lower and upper bounds of technical scores for sequestration practices, by management type
S_{min}, S_{max}	Lower and upper bounds of the potential sequestration range for the given management type

The values of E_{min} , E_{max} , S_{min} and S_{max} , are defined based on the technical ranges associated with each management regime (Table 5).

The values of P_E , P_S , $P_{E\ min}$, $P_{E\ max}$, $P_{S\ min}$ and $P_{S\ max}$ are determined through the technical checklist of agricultural practices, weighted according to the criteria established in Tables 2 and 3.

5.4. Projected Net Carbon Emission Limit (PNCEL)

Based on the estimated net emissions value for the baseline year (EL_0), the model projects a guiding limit for net carbon emissions in subsequent years, with the aim of progressively guiding the producer toward carbon neutrality by 2050. This projection is operationalized through a continuous decreasing trajectory, calculated from the estimated annual net emissions EL_0 which results from the difference between the estimated gross emissions (E_i) and the estimated carbon sequestration potential (S_i).

The model logic assumes that, once the net emissions value is known for the baseline year t_0 , it is possible to establish, for each subsequent year t , a maximum admissible limit for net emissions compatible with the target of total neutrality by 2050. The projection adopts, by default, a linear decreasing function, represented by the following equation:

$$PNCEL = EL_0 \times \left(1 - \frac{t - t_0}{2050 - t_0}\right)$$

Where:

PNCEL: Projected Net Carbon Emission Limit.

In this equation, *PNCEL* represents the projected net emission limit for year t , while EL_0 corresponds to the estimated net emissions in the reference year t_0 , which marks the starting point of the simulation and is not necessarily a fixed calendar year. The expression ensures that, by the

end of the period—i.e., in the year 2050—the value of *PNCEL* reaches zero, symbolizing the goal of carbon neutrality.

To account for the inherent variability of agricultural production systems and allow for greater interpretive flexibility, the model introduces variation bands of $\pm 5\%$ around the annual projected limit. These bands are defined as follows:

Where:

PNCEL⁺: upper bound of the Projected Net Carbon Emission Limit (PNCEL), representing a 5% tolerance above the annual target.

$$PNCEL^+ = PNCEL \times 1,05$$

PNCEL⁻: Lower bound of the Projected Net Carbon Emission Limit (PNCEL), representing a 5% tolerance below the annual target.

$$PNCEL^- = PNCEL \times 0,95$$

The annual net carbon emission estimated for year t ($EL_t = E_{i,t} - S_{i,t}$) can then be compared to the tolerance range defined by the bands *PNCEL*⁺ and *PNCEL*⁻, allowing the producer's performance to be classified into three interpretive categories:

- Above-target performance: $EL_t < PNCEL^-$;
- Within acceptable range: $PNCEL^- \leq EL_t \leq PNCEL^+$;
- Below-target performance (correction needed): $EL_t > PNCEL^+$.

This annual assessment mechanism not only provides technical guidance to the producer regarding the desirable level of net emissions for the following cycle, but also enables continuous and adjustable monitoring of progress. The trajectory toward carbon neutrality is thus constructed year by year, based on the actual dynamics of implemented agricultural practices, allowing for simulations of different management strategies and projections of future scenarios grounded in technical evidence.

5.5. Typological Characterization of Producer Profiles

For the initial parameterization of the PNCEL model applied to viticulture in the Douro region, the characterization of sub-regions by farm size (IVDP, 2025) was used. This source provides the distribution of winegrowing holdings by area range, disaggregated by the three sub-regions of the Douro Demarcated Region (RDD): Baixo Corgo, Cima Corgo, and Douro Superior. Additionally, the 2019 Agricultural Censu (INE, 2021), offered a structured overview of landholding composition and farm profiles in Portugal, contributing to the support of the adopted typology.

Based on this foundation, the area ranges were aggregated into three typological groups (Table 7), considering the total area per farm in hectares, in alignment with the actual distribution of holdings and supported by complementary references describing the production practices associated with each size category.

This three-dimensional segmentation enables the model to capture the heterogeneity of the Douro's productive landscape, reflecting the diversity of technical, structural, and environmental capacities among different types of producers in the region. A synthetic characterization of each group is presented below.

Table 7. Characterization of the type of producer profile.

Profile	Area range
Small producer	up to 2 ha
Medium producer	>2 ha up to 10 ha
Large producer	>20 ha

6. Simulation of the PNCEL Model by Producer Profile

6.1. Simulation Objective

The purpose of this simulation is to demonstrate the applicability and analytical capacity of the PNCEL model through the construction of representative technical scenarios for three typological profiles of wine producers in the Douro Demarcated Region (RDD): small, medium, and large. The simulation is carried out over a ten-year horizon (2024–2033), allowing for a continuous evaluation of net emission trajectories and the progressive alignment of each producer with the model’s projected annual carbon limits. It is crucial to emphasize that all data used for these simulations are hypothetical and projected, deliberately constructed to represent distinct management scenarios rather than direct measurements from real-world farms.

Each profile is constructed based on a technical inventory of agricultural practices implemented, accounting for both negative impacts (emissions) and positive contributions (carbon sequestration). The resulting scores are used to classify the producer under one of three management regimes (conventional, conservationist, or regenerative), which determine the parameters used in the interpolation of gross emissions (E_i) and potential sequestration (S_i) values. The annual net emission ($EL_t = E_{i,t} - S_{i,t}$) is then compared to the net emission limit projected by the model for year t ($PNCEL$), based on the goal of achieving carbon neutrality by 2050.

This simulation thus enables an evaluation of the dynamic response of each technical profile to the climate requirements imposed by the model, analyzing the results in terms of exceeding, meeting, or failing to meet the annual target. Each producer’s trajectory is presented through quantitative indicators, comparative tables, and graphical visualizations, enabling a critical analysis of the relative performance among profiles and the model’s sensitivity to gradual changes in agricultural practices.

6.2. Criteria for Constructing Technical Profiles

The definition of the technical profiles simulated in this study is based on the typological characterization of wine producers in the Douro Demarcated Region (DDR), as presented in Table 7, and on the progressive incorporation of agricultural practices representative of each segment.

The construction of these profiles followed operational, empirical, and scientific criteria that allowed the diversity of production strategies to be translated into realistic and technically interpretable trajectories within the PNCEL model.

For each typological profile (small, medium, and large producer), a scenario of agricultural practice transitions was developed over a ten-year horizon. The simulation was designed to reflect:

- i. The expected evolution of management based on the degree of technification and investment capacity associated with the scale of production;
- ii. The incremental adoption of less emissive and/or more sequestering practices, according to the operational feasibility of each profile;
- iii. Internal coherence between adopted practices, classified management type (conventional, conservationist, regenerative), and the corresponding scores;
- iv. Consistency with the interpolation structure and annual net emission calculation described in Section 5.3;
- v. Progressive alignment with the projected limits defined by the PNCEL model in Section 5.4, allowing assessment of whether and how each profile approaches carbon neutrality by 2050.

The transition between management regimes was designed based on technically plausible progressions. For example, the small producer profile starts with conservationist practices and gradually evolves toward regenerative management in the later years, with net emission values shifting from positive to slightly negative (indicating carbon sink conditions). The medium producer begins with conventional management and transitions toward conservationist practices. The large producer, on the other hand, shows a greater capacity for technological adoption, incorporating regenerative practices at a faster pace.

All technical parameters used—scores, emission and sequestration ranges, interpolation limits—are drawn directly from Tables 2 to 5. This structure ensures that the simulation reflects not only the model's applicability but also its methodological robustness and sensitivity to the nuances of the agricultural context.

6.3. Simulation Results by Producer Profile

The following results present the practical application of the model for three winegrower profiles in the Douro Demarcated Region: small, medium, and large producers. For each profile, a 10-year simulation was carried out based on a realistic progression of agricultural practices and management transitions. The estimated annual net emission (*EL*) was calculated through linear interpolation based on the scores obtained, as described in Section 5.3, and compared to the projected net carbon emission limits (*PNCEL*), as defined in Section 5.4. This approach makes it possible to assess each profile's performance trajectory and verify its compliance with the carbon neutrality goal by 2050.

6.3.1. Comparative Analysis Among Simulated Profiles

The comparative analysis of the three simulated profiles—small, medium, and large producers—makes it possible to evaluate how different scales of operation and adoption dynamics of agricultural practices impact performance in relation to the projected net carbon emission limit (*PNCEL*). The 10-year trajectory considered for each profile highlights important contrasts in technical progression, carbon sequestration effectiveness, and capacity to meet the decarbonization targets established by the model.

Table 8 illustrates the PNCEL model's ability to distinguish, classify, and project distinct technical trajectories over a 10-year period. The simulated profile begins with a low technical score (score 25), classified as conventional management, and consistently evolves to a regenerative regime (score 96).

The model adequately reflects this evolution, shown by the progressive reduction in *EL* (annual net emissions), which drops from 20.8 to 2.08 Mg CO₂-eq/ha/year, surpassing the lower projected limit (*PNCEL*⁻) starting in 2029.

The model’s functional robustness is further demonstrated in 2027, when it detects a regression in the technical score (score 48), resulting in a deviation from the desired trajectory and classification as “Below target.” This response confirms the model’s sensitivity to fluctuations in technical performance and the validity of its tolerance band system (*PNCEL*⁺; *PNCEL*⁻).

Table 8. Integrated simulation of the *PNCEL* model – Small producer (Mg CO₂-eq/ha/year).

Year	Technical Score	Type of Management	<i>E_i</i>	<i>S_i</i>	<i>EL</i>	<i>PNCEL</i>	<i>PNCEL</i> ⁻	<i>PNCEL</i> ⁺	Performance
2023	25	Conventional	21,75	0,95	20,8	20,8	19,76	21,84	Baseline
2024	32	Conventional	20,88	1,2	19,68	18,93	17,98	19,87	Within the range
2025	45	Conventional	19,45	1,81	17,64	17,06	16,21	17,91	Within the range
2026	52	Conservationist	9,4	4,4	5	15,18	14,42	15,94	Above target
2027	48	Conventional	18,96	1,73	17,23	13,31	12,64	13,98	Below target
2028	65	Conservationist	7,25	5,75	1,5	11,44	10,87	12,01	Above target
2029	78	Regenerative	2,59	8,56	-5,97	9,57	9,09	10,05	Above target
2030	85	Regenerative	2,18	9,8	-7,62	7,69	7,31	8,07	Above target
2031	89	Regenerative	1,97	10,36	-8,39	5,82	5,53	6,11	Above target
2032	94	Regenerative	1,73	11,12	-9,39	3,95	3,75	4,15	Above target
2033	96	Regenerative	1,65	11,28	-9,63	2,08	1,98	2,18	Above target

Figure 1 visually synthesizes the simulated trajectory, showing that the model effectively and intelligibly captures the dynamics of net emission reduction as a function of technical progression.

The *EL* curve (red line) progressively crosses the defined tolerance bands (*PNCEL*⁺ and *PNCEL*⁻), parameterization. The linear slope of the *PNCEL* trajectory reinforces the model’s deterministic structure, while the *EL* responses demonstrate the effectiveness of the interpolation method based on technical scoring.

The graph validates the model’s interpretive utility: it allows for the identification of deviations, recognition of progress, and performance classification based on objective technical criteria. Its visual clarity and explanatory power make it suitable for technical communication, audits, or participatory territorial management.

Figure 1. Evolution of Annual Net Emissions Relative to the Projected Limit (PNCEL) – Small Producer (Mg CO₂-eq/ha/year).

The simulation presented in Table 9 tests the PNCEL model’s capacity to handle scenarios in which the agroecological transition occurs at a later stage. The simulated profile remains under conventional management for five years, with low technical scores (score 20–48), before beginning a transition to conservation practices.

During the years 2026 and 2027, the projected target is exceeded ($EL > PNCEL^+$), demonstrating that the model effectively functions as an early-warning system for critical deviations. The interpretive response is accurate and consistent with the tolerance band system.

From 2028 onward, technical progression becomes evident (score ≥ 55), which reduces net emissions and repositions performance first within the acceptable range and later below $PNCEL^-$, validating the benchmarking mechanism: the model is capable of identifying and classifying technical improvements even after previous deviations.

Table 9. Integrated Simulation of the PNCEL Model – Medium Producer (Mg CO₂-eq/ha/year).

Year	Technical Score	Type of Management	E_i	S_i	EL	$PNCEL$	$PNCEL^-$	$PNCEL^+$	Performance
2023	20	Conventional	22,2	0,86	21,34	21,34	20,27	22,41	Baseline
2024	28	Conventional	21,08	1,1	19,98	19,42	18,45	20,39	Within the range
2025	35	Conventional	20,35	1,33	17,02	17,51	16,63	18,39	Above target
2026	42	Conventional	19,62	1,56	18,06	15,59	14,81	16,37	Below target
2027	48	Conventional	18,96	1,73	17,23	13,67	12,99	14,35	Below target
2028	55	Conservationist	8,75	4,75	4	11,76	11,17	12,35	Above target
2029	62	Conservationist	7,4	5,7	1,7	9,84	9,35	10,33	Above target
2030	68	Conservationist	6,8	6,2	0,6	7,92	7,52	8,32	Above target
2031	71	Conservationist	6,55	6,45	0,1	6,01	5,71	6,31	Above target
2032	74	Conservationist	6	7,5	-1,5	4,09	3,89	4,29	Above target
2033	72	Conservationist	6,2	6,8	-0,6	2,17	2,06	2,28	Above target

Figure 2 complements Table 9 by illustrating the model’s adaptive response to delays in the adoption of good practices. The red line (*EL*) remains near or above the solid blue line (*PNCEL*) during the first five years, reflecting the inertia of the simulated technical system.

Once conservation practices are adopted, the model reacts with a clear reduction in net emissions and progressive classification within or below the tolerance zone. The *PNCEL*⁺ and *PNCEL*⁻ bands continue to play a central interpretive role, allowing continuous tracking of both deviations and improvements.

This configuration demonstrates that the *PNCEL* model remains functional even in scenarios of delayed technical progress, with the ability to recalculate and reflect real performance transitions. The simulation validates the model as a useful tool for guiding medium-term strategies, promoting adjustments, and identifying critical turning points in technical performance.

Figure 2. Evolution of Annual Net Emissions in Relation to the Projected Limit (*PNCEL*) – Medium Producer (Mg CO₂-eq/ha/year).

The simulation of the large producer (Table 10) serves as a stress test for the model, assessing its ability to identify persistent underperformance. The simulated profile maintains conventional management throughout the ten-year period, with only incremental technical improvements (scores ranging from 15 to 49), and no strategic shift in practices.

Under the corrected logic — where the annual performance is benchmarked against the *PNCEL* limit projected in the previous year — the model classifies the profile as “Below target” from 2025 onward. This means the estimated net emissions (*EL*) exceeded not only the central target but also the upper tolerance limit (*PNCEL*⁺) of the model.

This consistent misalignment highlights the robustness of the model alert mechanism and the diagnostic sensitivity of its tolerance structure. The model clearly distinguishes between marginal improvements and structural transformations, maintaining a critical classification as long as the profile fails to meet projected goals.

The simulation underscores the model’s policy relevance: it effectively flags situations where the continuity of current practices is mathematically incompatible with climate mitigation targets — providing a clear rationale for targeted incentives, technical assistance, or regulatory measures to support the agroecological transition.

Tabela 10. Integrated PNCEL Model Simulation – Large Producer (Mg CO₂-eq/ha/year).

Year	Technical Score	Type of Management	E_i	S_i	EL	$PNCEL$	$PNCEL^-$	$PNCEL^+$	Performance
2023	15	Conventional	22,65	0,77	21,88	21,88	20,79	22,97	Baseline
2024	18	Conventional	22,47	0,82	21,65	19,91	18,91	20,91	Within the range
2025	22	Conventional	21,82	0,9	20,92	17,93	17,03	18,83	Below target
2026	26	Conventional	21,38	0,99	20,39	15,96	15,16	16,76	Below target
2027	30	Conventional	20,7	1,14	19,56	13,99	13,29	14,69	Below target
2028	35	Conventional	20,35	1,33	17,02	12,01	11,41	12,61	Below target
2029	38	Conventional	19,78	1,43	16,35	10,04	9,54	10,54	Below target
2030	42	Conventional	19,62	1,56	16,06	8,07	7,67	8,47	Below target
2031	45	Conventional	19,45	1,81	15,64	6,09	5,79	6,39	Below target
2032	47	Conventional	19,23	1,69	15,54	4,12	3,91	4,33	Below target
2033	49	Conventional	19,01	1,77	15,24	2,15	2,04	2,26	Below target

Figure 3 illustrates the corrected dynamic between net emissions (EL) and projected limits ($PNCEL$) for the large producer. Once the proper temporal alignment is applied — where the emission in year t is assessed against the target projected in year $t - 1$ — it becomes evident that, from 2025 onward, net emissions systematically exceed the upper tolerance bound ($PNCEL^+$).

Despite gradual technical improvements and slight reductions in emissions, the producer’s trajectory remains structurally misaligned with the decarbonization pathway. This underscores the model’s robustness as a continuous alert mechanism, capable of detecting early and persistent deviations from projected goals, even when the absolute values of emissions show moderate improvement.

The chart confirms that without a strategic transition — such as the adoption of conservationist or regenerative practices — the model algorithmically identifies the scenario as incompatible with the carbon neutrality target. PNCEL thus functions not only as a benchmarking and monitoring tool, but also as a decision-support system, helping stakeholders distinguish between marginal improvements and truly transformative progress.

By signaling persistent underperformance beyond the tolerance range, the model justifies the need for targeted interventions, such as incentives, technical support, or regulatory instruments, especially for structurally constrained producers.

Figure 3. Annual net emission trajectory in relation to the projected limit (*PNCEL*) – Large-scale producer (Mg CO₂-eq/ha/year).

Overall, the data confirm that the *PNCEL* model is sensitive to different paces and strategies of agro-environmental transition and is capable of accurately reflecting the cumulative effects of the practices adopted. Furthermore, it reinforces that achieving carbon neutrality by 2050 is feasible for all simulated profiles, provided there is a continuous technical transformation effort aligned with the guidelines for emission reduction and carbon sequestration.

6.3.2. Limitations and Potential Improvement of the Model

Although the *PNCEL* model demonstrated robust and coherent performance in simulating differentiated net carbon emission trajectories in viticulture, it contains inherent limitations related to its methodological design and current level of maturity. Recognizing these limitations is essential not only to frame the interpretation of results but also to guide future improvements.

The first limitation concerns the theoretical nature of the simulated data used in the trajectories of each producer profile. Although the input values were assigned based on well-established scientific references and adjusted to the agronomic reality of the Douro Demarcated Region, the absence of complete empirical time series—drawn from actual carbon inventories—restricts the external validity of the results. Transitioning to full empirical application requires validating the model with field data, preferably across multiple growing cycles and under different edaphoclimatic conditions.

Another important limitation is the reliance on self-declared agricultural practices in the technical checklist. Although the scoring structure is grounded in scientific evidence and calibrated by management categories, the accuracy of the diagnostic depends on the truthfulness and precision of the information provided by producers. This issue becomes especially sensitive in contexts involving audits, subsidy allocation, or environmental certifications, where responses may be less reliable due to regulatory incentives. In such cases, integration with external verification tools—such as remote sensors, satellite imagery, meteorological data, and digital tracking platforms—represents a viable and necessary pathway to ensure transparency and methodological integrity.

The assignment of weights to agricultural practices is also a critical point. While it was based on three technical criteria (magnitude, frequency, and scope), the weighting process includes an interpretative component that may vary depending on the agronomic context, bibliographic sources, or the evolution of scientific knowledge. The use of formal multi-criteria analysis methods or supervised learning algorithms with validated empirical data could strengthen this component, reducing subjectivity and increasing the precision of future estimates.

Finally, the model could benefit from the use of stochastic simulations, such as the Monte Carlo method, to test the sensitivity of outputs to variations in input parameters. This approach would allow for the estimation of confidence intervals for net emissions and projected limits, explicitly incorporating uncertainty associated with climatic, operational, and technical factors. As a result, PNCEL would evolve from being merely a deterministic model with a fixed tolerance band to also serving as a probabilistic tool for climate risk management.

Despite these limitations, the PNCEL model demonstrates strong potential for refinement and expansion. Its modular and transparent structure facilitates adaptation to other crops, territorial contexts, or climate mitigation goals. It may even be integrated into territorial monitoring platforms, payment for ecosystem services schemes, voluntary certification programs, or green financing instruments.

By combining operational simplicity—ensured by its modular structure based on technical checklists—with methodological rigor—reflected in its linear normalization, continuous interpolation, and technical-emissions ranges—and territorial scalability—enabled by its typological producer profiling and independence from direct inventory requirements—PNCEL positions itself as a promising tool to support the agroecological transition and agricultural decarbonization in the context of the climate emergency.

7. Applications of the PNCEL Model in Climate and Agro-Environmental Public Policies

The operationalization of the PNCEL model as a climate diagnostic tool makes it particularly relevant for application in public policies aimed at emission mitigation and the promotion of sustainable agricultural practices, addressing the existing gap in accessible quantification and projection of the carbon balance. By translating concrete agricultural practices into standardized estimates of net carbon emissions, the model provides a functional, comparable, and easily interpretable indicator for technicians, managers, and policymakers.

Firstly, PNCEL can be used as a sectoral climate monitoring instrument, providing an annualized metric of net carbon emissions in viticultural production units, as well as the ability to project future scenarios based on varying levels of practice adoption. This capability is particularly valuable for the development of regional or national agricultural emissions inventories, enabling the assessment of the effectiveness of implemented measures, the identification of progress or setbacks in the decarbonization trajectory, and the comparison of performance across regions or management systems.

In addition, the model can be incorporated as an eligibility or prioritization criterion in agro-environmental financing programs. Public policies such as the eco-schemes of the Common Agricultural Policy – CAP (Conselho da União Europeia, n.d.), the CAP Strategic Plan 2023–2027 (Gabinete de Planeamento, n.d.), or initiatives like 4p1000 (International “4 per 1000” Initiative, n.d.) could use PNCEL to establish progressive climate performance targets and link financial incentives to the achievement of those targets, within a performance-based environmental payment system—mirroring the logic used in normative indices such as the Carbon Balance Index (Dekay, 2017). The methodological features of PNCEL, including its continuous interpolation and $\pm 5\%$ tolerance range, provide the flexibility needed to accommodate operational variations while maintaining the diagnostic integrity required by such programs (Pascual et al., 2021).

Another potential application lies in the use of PNCEL as a technical tool for rural extension and agronomic advisory services, enabling farmers to annually assess their climate performance and plan adjustments based on objective criteria, by simulating the impact of different practice adoption scenarios on their carbon footprint. This function is particularly strategic in territories with a strong presence of small and medium-sized producers, where access to complex diagnostics is limited, and where models such as PNCEL can fill critical operational gaps and contribute to the implementation of agro-environmental targets aligned with the guidelines of the 4p1000 program (International “4 per 1000” Initiative, n.d.; Villat & Nicholas, 2023).

However, the institutional adoption of the PNCEL model requires certain conditions. A primary challenge is the establishment of robust mechanisms for verifying reported practices, whether through structured self-declaration, technical audits, or cross-referencing with official records. It is also advisable to align the model with national GHG monitoring systems, such as agricultural sector inventories and land-use registries. Furthermore, its use as a regulatory tool will depend on the ability of public policies to integrate agronomic and climate variables within a coherent regulatory framework—overcoming the traditional divide between agricultural and environmental policies, a point already discussed in the introduction of this study in light of the gaps identified in European and Portuguese legislation on soil conservation (Heuser, 2022; Leite, 2025).

The structure of the PNCEL model—based on agricultural practices, parametric interpolation, and tolerance ranges—positions it as a transition tool for shifting from conventional agricultural systems to low-carbon and regenerative models. It is capable of aligning with agendas such as the European Green Deal (European Commission, n.d.), the Sustainable Development Goals, particularly Goal 13 (ODS13, n.d.) and Goals 15 (ODS15, n.d.), and the commitments outlined in national emissions inventories. Its applicability to different producer profiles and its ability to simulate gradual management transitions reinforce its potential as both a technical and policy instrument to support the sustainable transformation of the agricultural sector.

In summary, the PNCEL model presents itself as a technical tool with the potential to be integrated into a wide range of public policy instruments, from local to EU levels, offering support for environmental performance assessment, the redirection of agro-environmental subsidies, and the implementation of territorial climate targets. However, for this integration to be effective and institutionally legitimate, soil must be formally recognized as a strategic ecological infrastructure, and semi-quantitative models such as PNCEL must be incorporated into existing regulatory frameworks. This need becomes even more evident in light of recent developments such as Regulation (EU) 2024/3012 (European Parliament and Council, 2024), which establishes a certification framework for carbon sequestration practices, and the European Climate Law (European Parliament and Council, 2021), which legally enshrines climate neutrality as a binding target for all Member States by 2050. The absence of legal instruments that connect productive practices to climate certification mechanisms undermines the full utilization of tools such as PNCEL, thus requiring a critical analysis of the regulatory barriers and opportunities in this field.

8. Challenges and Gaps in Soil Regulation for Climate Policies

This section aims to critically examine the regulatory framework governing soil in the European Union and in Portugal, considering its strategic relevance for climate change mitigation and for the integration of technical tools such as the PNCEL Model into public policies. Based on a cross-reading between the ecological foundations of soil and its legal status, it is argued that significant institutional barriers remain to its operationalization as a climate asset, despite recent advances at the European Union level.

Soil is an ecological resource with multiple and interdependent functions—such as water regulation, biodiversity support, and carbon storage—that are fundamental to the resilience of agri-food systems (Blum, 2005; FAO, 2015). These functions are widely recognized in the

literature as essential to the provision of ecosystem services (Adhikari & Hartemink, 2016; Vrebos et al., 2017). However, from a legal standpoint, soil remains subject to a fragmented regulatory framework, lacking a dedicated European framework directive, which results in weak and poorly integrated normative protection (Glæsner et al., 2014; Paleari, 2017; Heuser, 2022).

This regulatory gap has direct practical consequences: it hinders the development of coherent soil-based climate mitigation policies and complicates the incorporation of technical management and monitoring tools, such as the PNCEL Model. The absence of explicit normative targets for soil conservation or carbon sequestration is one of the key limitations identified in the literature (Ronchi et al., 2019).

Despite this scenario, two recent legislative references from the European Union represent a significant turning point. The first is the European Climate Law (European Parliament and Council, 2021), which establishes climate neutrality as a legally binding objective by 2050, with intermediate targets of a 55% net emissions reduction by 2030. The second is Regulation (EU) 2024/3012 (European Parliament and Council, 2024), which establishes a voluntary certification framework for permanent carbon removals, carbon farming, and carbon storage in products. This regulation defines criteria for quantification, additionality, permanence, and environmental co-benefits—all of which are compatible with the operational parameters of the PNCEL Model.

In this context, PNCEL may play an instrumental role as a technical-scientific diagnostic tool adaptable to the logic of standardized baselines required by the certification regulation. The annual practice-based interpolation already operationalized in the model is compatible with the regulatory approach proposed for sequestration and emission reduction activities in agricultural soils. Furthermore, the model can serve as a preliminary support mechanism for the eligibility of practices within certification schemes, particularly with regard to verification by independent audits and the traceability of climate benefits.

This technical interoperability capacity of the model aligns with the requirements established by international frameworks such as the GHG Protocol, which defines reporting structures for direct, indirect, and diffuse emissions (Scopes 1, 2, and 3), demanding methodological consistency, transparency, and auditability (The Greenhouse Gas Protocol, 2004). Additionally, ISO 14064-3:2019 (ISO, 2019) sets specific criteria for the independent verification of GHG assertions, which can be met by models like PNCEL, provided that their data structure and supporting evidence adhere to the principles of sufficiency, impartiality, and documentary coherence.

In the Portuguese context, the situation is even more delicate. National legislation does not grant soil a distinct legal status, treating it in a fragmented manner across sectoral codes and regulations. As Leite (2025), argues, there is a structural gap in Portuguese soil legislation, both in the legal recognition of its ecological functions and in the provision of positive regulatory mechanisms—such as the certification of agricultural practices with climate benefits. This observation is supported by studies that highlight the absence of legal instruments encouraging soil conservation and regeneration practices in policy tools such as Territorial Action Programs or the CAP Strategic Plan (Rodrigues et al., 2009; Castelo-Grande et al., 2018).

Therefore, for models such as PNCEL to be effectively integrated into climate and agro-environmental public policies, three main challenges must be addressed: (i) the absence of a binding European legal framework on soils; (ii) the lack of institutionalization of climate certification mechanisms in the Portuguese context; and (iii) the lack of integration between technical carbon sequestration diagnostics and CAP incentive programs. Overcoming these barriers requires the recognition of soil as strategic ecological infrastructure and the creation of regulatory instruments that enable its active management based on scientific evidence and modeling tools such as PNCEL.

9. Concluding remarks

This study presented the methodological development and conceptual framework of the PNCEL Model, a technical-scientific tool aimed at the annual quantification of carbon emissions and sequestration in agricultural and agroforestry systems, with a focus on the viticulture sector. By proposing a methodology based on the weighted scoring of agricultural practices and parameterized interpolation across management bands, the model enables continuous and comparable diagnostics of climate performance at the production unit level. The articulation of technical knowledge, empirical evidence, and an operational decision-making structure sets PNCEL apart from normative or purely spatial models, consolidating its utility as a support tool for local and regional environmental management.

Among its main advances, the model stands out for its ability to operate based on qualitative data (adopted practices) and generate semi-quantitative results adjusted to management profiles, while respecting existing productive diversity. The simulations conducted with different types of producers demonstrated the model's sensitivity in identifying consistent net emission patterns and its potential to inform strategic decisions—from agroecological transition to access to climate certification mechanisms. Its alignment with recent regulatory frameworks of the European Union, such as Regulation (EU) 2024/3012 (European Parliament and Council, 2024) and the European Climate Law (European Parliament and Council, 2021), reinforces the institutional relevance of the model and its capacity to interface with environmental and agri-food public policies.

Despite its advances, the model presents acknowledged limitations, particularly regarding the empirical assignment of weights to practices, its reliance on self-reported data, and the need for validation across diverse territorial contexts. Future stages of the project should prioritize calibration with real field data, integration with remote monitoring systems, and the incorporation of multi-annual practices. Additionally, the development of simplified computational interfaces is recommended to enhance the model's usability by technicians, producers, and policymakers.

The PNCEL Model thus represents an innovative, pragmatic, and adaptable proposal aligned with the demands of the climate transition in agriculture. By combining technical precision with institutional applicability, it serves as a strategic tool to enable carbon neutrality commitments within the productive sector and to strengthen territorial climate governance.

Acknowledgments | This work was developed under the Science4Policy 2023 (S4P-23): annual science for policy project call, an initiative by PlanAPP – Competence Centre for Planning, Policy and Foresight in Public Administration in partnership with the Foundation for Science and Technology, financed by Portugal's Recovery and Resilience Plan.

Conflicts of interest | The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Annex

Institutional Applicability Framework of the PNCEL Model

The PNCEL model was developed as a technical-scientific tool to continuously and comparably estimate the net carbon balance in agricultural and agroforestry systems, based on a scoring system of productive practices and interpolation within parameterized ranges. Beyond its methodological robustness, the model possesses attributes that make it operationally compatible with regulatory, programmatic, and certification requirements across various institutional scales.

The following Table A1 presents a systematic analysis of the main relevant institutional instruments, considering their scale of operation, technical requirements, purpose, and the potential contribution of the PNCEL model. This framework was built based on the cross-referencing of the explicit requirements of standards and programs with the functionalities of the model.

Table A1. Institutional Compatibility of the PNCEL Model.

Instrument / Program	Scale of Application	Technical Requirement	Institutional Purpose	Potential Contribution of PNCEL
Regulation (EU) 2024/3012 (European Parliament and Council, 2024)	European Union	Verifiable quantification of removals and emissions	Voluntary certification of agricultural carbon practices	Technical pre-diagnosis with validated interpolation
European Climate Law (European Parliament and Council, 2021)	EU / Member State	Annual sectoral monitoring, binding targets	National climate planning, LULUCF, and inventories	Annual metric generator compatible with sectoral aggregation
Portugal's CSP 2023–2027 (PEPAC) (Gabinete de Planeamento, n.d.)	National	Justification of eligibility and agri-environmental practices	Access to sustainable management and climate support schemes	Diagnostic tool for technical alignment
Portuguese LTS 2050 (RNC2050 Strategy) (RNC2050, n.d.)	National	Longitudinal assessment of net emissions by sector	Definition of sectoral climate neutrality pathways	Performance classification and annual scenario modeling
International “4 per 1000” Initiative (International “4 per 1000” Initiative, n.d.)	International	Annual sequestration estimate and cross-regional comparability	Voluntary participation in international networks	Semi-quantitative method parameterized by management type

This matrix demonstrates that the PNCEL model, beyond serving as a technical-operational index, aligns normatively with the current regulatory frameworks of the European Union and the programmatic requirements at the national level. It can thus be incorporated both into climate mitigation strategies and into agro-environmental support and certification mechanisms, particularly due to its adaptability and low operational cost within the context of agroforestry systems management.